

PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS OF LEGAL AWARENESS, AND LEGAL SOCIALIZATION**Khalilova Teybe Rauf***Phd student; Department of Psychology;
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Legal consciousness plays an important role in the functioning of law and its social action. Legal norms cannot directly influence people's behavior if they are not recognized and accepted by individual legal consciousness. The process of recognizing legal norms and refraction through the prism of legal consciousness has an individual psychological nature.

Differences in people's behavior, even with formally identical ideas about legal norms and their content, are explained by different degrees of perception and interiorization of these norms in their individual consciousness, especially in legal consciousness. The motivation for different types of behavior (law-abiding or unlawful) reflects different manifestations of perception and attitude to legal norms in individual consciousness.

The paper is descriptive analyzing that has been developed according to literature materials are related to this topic.

Keywords: legal consciousness, social actions, awareness, psychological components

Literature review: Legal consciousness, like any humanitarian semantic concept, is one of those phenomena that cannot be fully disclosed in one system of ideas. At the initial stage of the introduction of the concept of "legal consciousness" into science, it did not yet have any completely separate content. In particular, the German legal school used the definitions "legal feeling" or "legal experience" for a long time. The 19th century saw a growing interest in the psychological aspects of law and legal consciousness. During this period, works appeared devoted to the study of the moral and emotional foundations of law. One of the famous scientists who contributed to the study of legal consciousness was Wilhelm Wundt, who considered the issues of the psychological aspects of legal consciousness. Although Wundt did not develop a special theory of legal consciousness, in his works on psychology and consciousness, he identified elementary psychological processes such as perception, attention, memory and thinking, which play an important role in the perception and interpretation of legal norms, and also influence the processes of decision-making and the formation of legal beliefs.

A significant contribution to the study of the psychological aspects of legal consciousness was made by L.I. Petrazhitzky, the founder of the psychological theory of law, according to which the human psyche plays an important role in the development of society, including its legal sphere. In this theory, the category of law is considered taking into account psychological patterns, in particular, special attention is paid to the legal emotions of people. Entitlement emotions are experiences that are associated with a sense of entitlement to own or have a right to something, as well as a sense of obligation to perform certain actions.

Within the framework of the theory under consideration, all legal experiences can be divided into two types: positive and intuitive. Positive experiences are associated with the rights and obligations that are established by the state and enshrined in official legal

norms. Intuitive experiences, on the contrary, are associated with personal beliefs and internal feelings of correctness and justice. It is important to note that it is intuitive law that plays a regulatory role in human behavior.

The main emphasis in this theory is on psychological factors, in contrast to political, socio-economic and other aspects. This means that psychological states, emotions and beliefs of people play an important role in the formation and understanding of law. This understanding allows for a more in-depth study of the influence of psychological factors on legal behavior and decision-making in the legal sphere of society. In his works, I.A. Ilyin noted that "legal consciousness is an "instinctive sense of rights" in which one's own spirituality is realized and the spirituality of other people is recognized" [2, p. 310]. In the modern sense, legal consciousness refers to the system of ideas, knowledge, beliefs, values and expectations related to law and legal norms and is a complex combination of cognitive, emotional and motivational aspects that influence the way of perceiving, understanding and accepting legal norms and principles.

As V.A. Rybakov notes, "legal consciousness is a reflection of legal reality, its cognition and attitude towards it" [4, p. 28]. However, legal consciousness is not limited to a simple reflection or cognition of legal reality. It also includes the subjective perception and interpretation of law, the formation of value orientations, attitudes and motivations that influence the behavior and actions of an individual in the legal sphere.

This understanding of legal consciousness as a reflection of legal reality, its cognition and expression of attitude towards it can be considered simplified, because it does not take into account the complexity and versatility of the phenomenon of legal consciousness. Legal consciousness is a multidimensional and dynamic phenomenon. As Malakhov mentioned: "legal consciousness is the consciousness of law by a legal being, i.e. the self-consciousness of a legal being" [3, p. 4]. Legal consciousness can be considered as a special

form of consciousness associated with the awareness and understanding of law as such. It reflects the specific self-consciousness of an individual as a legal being, his conscious attitude to legal norms, values and principles. The author also rightly notes that "legal consciousness is not a means of cognition and not a mechanism of reflection" [3, p. 23]. Indeed, legal consciousness cannot be identified exclusively with a means of cognition or a mechanism of reflection of law. Legal consciousness is formed and developed in the process of interaction with the legal system and legal norms and represents a complex conscious attitude of an individual to legal reality, his conscious orientation towards compliance with legal norms and respect for legal principles. At the same time, law, as an existing legal system, reflects and refracts the legal consciousness of society, its values, needs and ideas about justice. Legal norms and legal practice can be a product of the formation and implementation of legal consciousness in society.

Thus, legal consciousness influences the formation and transformation of the legal system, and is not just a passive reflection of the law. It plays an active role in the formation of legal practice and influences how the law is applied and perceived in society.

The structure of legal consciousness as a psychological phenomenon includes several main components [6]:

- Firstly, this is a cognitive component associated with the cognitive sphere of the individual. It reflects the level of awareness and information about the law. In this aspect, the presence of legal information and knowledge of legal norms, procedures and processes is important;

- Secondly, the structure includes an emotional-value component associated with the emotional-personal sphere. Here, personal assessments, attitudes and value orientations to the law and its application are important, which includes emotional reactions, feelings, attitudes to legal norms and the process of law enforcement;

- Thirdly, the structure of legal consciousness includes a behavioral component associated with the motivational-behavioral sphere. Here we are talking about the ability and readiness to comply with legal norms, participate in legal procedures, and show other activity in the field of law.

Thus, the structure of legal consciousness includes cognitive, emotional-value and behavioral components. They are interconnected and influence each other, forming a conscious attitude towards the law and behavior in accordance with it.

Deep knowledge of the law plays a key role in the formation and development of the emotional-value and behavioral components of legal consciousness. Legal awareness, that is, understanding and knowledge of legal norms and procedures, is a fundamental factor for observing the law and maintaining legal discipline [7,8].

When a person has deep knowledge of the law, he is aware of his rights and obligations, and also understands how the legal system functions, which allows him to develop the emotional-value component of legal consciousness. Knowledge of the law forms emotional

connections and assessments associated with the perception of the content of legal norms. The better a person is informed about the law, the more likely it is that he will develop a positive attitude towards the law, value orientations and emotional reactions that support legal discipline.

In addition, deep knowledge of the law is the basis for the development of the behavioral element of legal consciousness. A person with deep knowledge of the law understands how to comply with legal regulations and how to act correctly in a given situation covered by the sphere of legal regulation. This contributes to the development of skills and readiness to demonstrate legal behavior, which in turn contributes to the maintenance of legal discipline in general.

Thus, deep knowledge of the law is the main prerequisite for the formation and development of the emotional-value and behavioral components of legal consciousness. It ensures not only an understanding of legal norms and procedures, but also contributes to the formation of a positive attitude towards the law, value orientations and readiness for legal behavior [8].

The second component of legal consciousness includes *value judgments, opinions and orientations* that are formed both on the basis of accumulated knowledge of the law and under the influence of various factors related to the legal sphere.

The emotional-value component of legal consciousness reflects personal preferences, views and judgments related to legal aspects. It is formed on the basis of acquired knowledge about law and legal norms, as well as under the influence of external factors such as social values, moral beliefs, social and cultural influences.

This component of legal consciousness is individual for each person. It reflects their subjective assessments and attitudes towards law, which can be formed under the influence of life experience, education, values and worldview. This component can also be formed through interaction with other people, social groups and social institutions [6].

As a result, the component of legal consciousness under consideration represents subjective assessments and views on law, which are formed on the basis of knowledge, experience and the influence of social factors. It plays an important role in shaping a person's attitude to law, his opinions on legal issues and orientation in the legal sphere.

The *motivational and behavioral component* in the structure of legal consciousness is the final link in the entire mechanism of formation of legal consciousness. It includes readiness, ability and skills of conscious behavior corresponding to the requirements of legal norms

This component manifests itself in real situations that have legal significance. It cannot exist separately from other components of legal consciousness and affects the process of formation of legal consciousness itself. The component under consideration is responsible for specific behavior of a person, which can be both normative-conformist and deviant [6,7].

The motivational and behavioral component of legal consciousness determines the degree of legal socialization of an individual. Legal socialization includes the assimilation of norms and values of the legal system, the formation of lawful behavior and responsibility before the law. Various psychological factors, such as motivation, emotions, cognitive processes and social influence, have a direct impact on motivation and behavior in relation to law, forming various levels of legal socialization [6].

This component has a wide range of possible manifestations, including various intermediate forms of behavior. It depends on many factors, such as personal beliefs, values, motivations, social environment and the context of a specific situation.

The *behavioral component* of the structure of legal consciousness is the last stage, where legal knowledge, emotional-value orientations and motivations are transformed into specific human behavior. This component is important for understanding the influence of legal consciousness on the actual behavior of an individual in the legal sphere.

Conclusion: Thus, the psychological components that influence legal consciousness have a complex and multifaceted nature. They can be associated with cognitive, emotional, motivational and personal aspects of a person [6, 9].

Psychological components are interconnected and interact with each other, forming the structure of legal consciousness. They determine how a person perceives, understands, evaluates and reacts to the law and legal norms. Identifying the role of psychological components helps to better understand why people have different attitudes toward law and how psychological factors can influence their behavior in the context of the legal system. The level of emotional stability, conformity, risk propensity, or empathy can influence how a person perceives and interprets legal norms.

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